

Chromophobe Renal Cell Carcinoma: Report of Two Cases with Contrasting Clinical Presentations

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ABSTRACT

We present two cases of chromophobe renal cell carcinoma (ChRCC) with contrasting clinical features. The first case involves a 38-year-old woman who presented with macroscopic hematuria and left flank pain. Imaging studies revealed an 11.5 cm left renal mass. She underwent radical nephrectomy, with a histopathological diagnosis of ISUP grade 2 chromophobe carcinoma, showing no vascular invasion or metastases and demonstrating good postoperative outcomes. The second case describes a 65-year-old man with left flank abdominal pain, in whom a 9.01 cm left renal mass adherent to the duodenum was identified during radical nephrectomy. Both cases highlight the clinical variability of this rare neoplasm, accounting for approximately 5% of malignant renal tumors. While the first case illustrates a typical presentation in younger patients, the second demonstrates more aggressive behavior with local invasion. These findings reinforce the importance of early histopathological diagnosis and individualized surgical management, as cases with local invasion features require close oncological follow-up.

KEYWORDS: Chromophobe Renal Cell Carcinoma; Renal neoplasms; Nephrectomy; Case report; Pathology; Pathology; Diagnostic imaging; Surgery; Histopathology.

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AIM

This study aims to describe two contrasting cases of ChRCC, emphasizing its clinical and pathological variability, and to discuss the implications for diagnosis, surgical management, and prognosis. By comparing a young patient with localized disease and an older patient with locally invasive features, we highlight the spectrum of this rare tumor and the need for tailored therapeutic approaches.

INTRODUCTION

Renal cell carcinoma (RCC) comprises a heterogeneous group of malignant neoplasms originating in the renal parenchyma, representing approximately 90% of primary renal tumors in adults⁴. Within this classification, distinct histological subtypes exist, each with unique morphological, genetic, and biological behaviors. Clear cell carcinoma is the most prevalent subtype, accounting for 70–80% of cases, followed by papillary carcinoma (10–15%) and, less commonly, chromophobe renal cell carcinoma (ChRCC), which represents approximately 5% of all RCCs¹.

ChRCC is distinguished by its unique histopathological features, including pale and granular cytoplasm, prominent

cell membranes, and nuclei that often appear "raisin-like" or binucleated⁵. Genetically, ChRCC is typically associated with multiple chromosomal losses (chromosomes 1, 2, 6, 10, 13, 17, and 21) and mutations in the TP53 gene and mTOR pathway-related genes, differing from the genetic alterations seen in other RCC subtypes^{6,7}.

Despite its malignant nature, ChRCC is generally considered a less aggressive variant with a more favorable prognosis compared to clear cell carcinoma, particularly when diagnosed at early stages and confined to the kidney². However, the clinical presentation of this neoplasm can vary significantly, ranging from incidental findings on imaging to specific symptoms or, rarely, more invasive behavior affecting prognosis^{3,8}.

This report describes two cases of ChRCC that, while confirming the low prevalence of this entity, strikingly illustrate its variability in clinical presentation and biological behavior. Both cases, with contrasting demographic, clinical, and pathological features, emphasize the importance of accurate and early histopathological diagnosis, as well as the need for individualized surgical management to optimize

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patient outcomes, even in a typically favorable-prognosis neoplasm.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Female Patient

A 38-year-old previously healthy woman, with no known toxic habits or family oncological history, presented in May 2023 with macroscopic hematuria (red urine with clots) and moderate-intensity left flank pain (6/10 on the visual analog scale). Hematuria resolved spontaneously after four days, but the pain persisted, prompting medical evaluation.

Diagnostic studies included a renal ultrasound (05/22/2023), which revealed a solid left renal mass suggestive of

malignancy. Subsequent CT urography (06/02/2023) confirmed a well-defined 10 × 10 cm left renal tumor displacing adjacent parenchyma, with no perirenal fat or adjacent structure invasion. A chest CT (07/27/2023) showed no pulmonary metastases.

On 08/04/2023, she underwent left radical nephrectomy. Intraoperative findings included an enlarged kidney (13 × 10 cm) with neovascularization but no adrenal or lymph node involvement. Histopathology confirmed ChRCC (ISUP grade 2), 11.5 × 10 cm, confined to the kidney without sarcomatoid/rhabdoid features, necrosis, or lymphovascular invasion. Surgical margins were negative.

Postoperative recovery was uneventful, with no recurrence at six-month follow-up.

Fig 1. Hematoxylin And Eosin Stained Section Shows Presence Of Cells With Pale Eosinophilic Granular Cytoplasm, Moderate Nuclear Atypia And Frequent Binucleated Or Multinucleated Cells.

Male Patient

A 65-year-old male motorcycle taxi driver, with no known toxic habits or family oncological history, presented in April 2024 with left flank abdominal pain 7/10 intensity radiating to the ipsilateral lumbar region, unresponsive to analgesics.

A thoraco-abdominopelvic CT (03/12/2025) revealed a 9.01 × 13.77 × 9 cm heterogeneous left renal mass with significant

contrast enhancement (85 HU), suggesting malignancy. Labs showed elevated hemoglobin 16.7 g/dL.

Left radical nephrectomy identified tumor adhesions to the duodenum, suggesting local extension. Postoperative course was uncomplicated, but close oncological follow-up was planned due to local invasion concerns.

Fig 2. Computed tomography (CT) scan of lesion: Soft tissue mass is dependent of the left kidney, which of the size was 9.01 × 13.77 × 9 cm

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DISCUSSION

ChRCC exhibits notable clinical variability. The first case of a young female presented classically with hematuria, pain, but no palpable mass, while the second case of a senior male had atypical pain-dominant symptoms. The female patient's localized tumor 11.5 cm, ISUP 2 contrasts with the male's locally invasive mass 9.01 × 13.77 × 9 cm, duodenal adhesions, underscoring ChRCC's unpredictable behavior. The male's elevated hemoglobin 16.7 g/dL may reflect paraneoplastic polycythemia, rare in ChRCC. Adhesions in the second case suggest higher recurrence risk, necessitating close surveillance.

CONCLUSION

These cases demonstrate that ChRCC, though rare, exhibits significant variability in age at presentation, clinical symptoms, and biological behavior. Early diagnosis and complete surgical resection remain the cornerstones of management, but locally invasive cases may require multidisciplinary approaches and close follow-up. Clinicians should maintain a high index of suspicion for ChRCC even in atypical presentations, as timely intervention can optimize outcomes in this generally favorable-prognosis malignancy. Early diagnosis and complete resection remain cornerstone treatments, but locally invasive cases may require multidisciplinary management.

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